

Mixed ligand complex formation of copper(II) with 2,5-diaminovaleric acid and some amino acids

M. Sivasankaran Nair^{*a}, G. Kalalakshmi^a and M. Sankaranarayana Pillai^b

^aDepartment of Chemistry, Manonmaniam Sundaranar University, Abishekapatti, Tirunelveli-627 012, India

^bDepartment of Chemistry, S. T. Hindu College, Nagercoil-629 002, India

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The stability and structure of the mixed ligand complexes formed by Cu^{II} with DL-2,5-diaminovaleric acid (dava) as ligand (A) and DL-2-aminobutanoic acid (2aba), DL-3-aminobutanoic acid (3aba), DL-4-aminobutanoic acid (4aba) and DL-4-amino-3-hydroxybutanoic acid (ahba) as ligands (B) are reported.

DL-2,5-Diaminovaleric acid (dava) otherwise known as ornithine, acts as a catalyst in the biological Krebs's urea process. The significance of DL-2-aminobutanoic acid (2aba), DL-3-aminobutanoic acid (3aba), DL-4-aminobutanoic acid (4aba) and DL-4-amino-3-hydroxybutanoic acid (ahba) are well known. The present communication reports mixed ligand complex formation of Cu^{II} with the titled ligands.

Results and Discussion

The CuABH and CuAB types of mixed ligand complexes in addition to the binary complexes due to ligands A and B (Table 1) are detected.

Stability and structure of CuABH complexes : Since only in the Cu^{II}-dava(A) and not in the Cu^{II}-2aba, 3aba, 4aba and ahba(B) binary systems the protonated binary species has been detected (Table 1), it can be inferred that in the CuABH species in Cu^{II}-dava(A)-2aba, 3aba, 4aba and ahba(B) systems, the extra proton is attached with dava(A) ligand. Then the log $\log K_{Cu(AH)B}^{CuAH}$ values obtained (Table 2) should be comparable with the respective log K_{CuB}^{Cu} values in the Cu^{II}-2aba, 3aba, 4aba and ahba(B) binary systems (Table 1). Actually, this is the case with the Cu^{II}-dava(A)-2aba, 3aba and 4aba(B) systems (Table 1). This indicates that 2aba, 3aba and 4aba ligands are bidentate in their Cu(AH)B complexes as is the case with their CuB binary species. In the case of ahba(B) ligand system, this parameter is ~4 log units less compared to the log β value of 13.02 for the CuB ahba binary species. This indicates a difference in the mode of binding of ahba(B) in the Cu(AH)B mixed ligand and CuB ahba binary species, i.e. in the Cu(AH)B species, ahba(B) is bidentate binding through the amino and hydroxo groups as is its binding in the CuB₂ binary species, though it is tridentate in its CuB binary species⁴. The different mode of binding of ahba in its binary and mixed ligand complex species is also reflected in the log $K_{Cu(AH)B}^{CuB}$ values obtained in the Cu^{II}-dava(A)-2aba, 3aba, 4aba and ahba(B) systems, i.e. in the

first three systems, the log $K_{Cu(AH)B}^{CuB}$ values (Table 2) bear favourable comparison with the log β_{CuAH} value in the Cu^{II}-dava(A) binary system⁴ (Table 1), demonstrating the same mode of coordination of protonated dava in both CuAH dava binary and Cu(AH)B mixed ligand complexes. The lower log $K_{Cu(AH)B}^{CuB}$ value obtained in the ahba(B) system can be accounted by considering the fact that in this system, this parameter has been calculated using log β_{CuA} value for the tridentate binding of ahba⁴, while as discussed above ahba is bidentate in the Cu(AH)B species.

Table 1. Stability constants for the Cu^{II} complexes of dava, 2aba, 3aba, 4aba and ahba binary systems*

Temp. 37°, I = 0.15 mol dm⁻³ (NaClO₄)

Parameter	dava ^a	2aba ^b	3aba ^b	4aba ^b	ahba ^a
log β_{HB}	10.22(1)	9.43(1)	9.95(1)	10.51(1)	12.88(11)
log β_{H_2A}	18.85(2)	11.54(1)	13.30(1)	14.24(1)	21.91(2)
log β_{H_3A}	29.99(4)	—	—	—	25.78(3)
log β_{CuBH}	17.67(2)	—	—	—	—
log β_{CuB}	—	8.10(2)	7.16(2)	6.07(9)	13.02(9)
log $\beta_{CuB_2A_2}$	34.32(3)	—	—	—	—
log β_{CuB_2H}	26.12(6)	—	—	—	—
log β_{CuB_2}	—	15.13(4)	12.90(5)	—	19.09(24)
log $\beta_{Cu_2B_2}$	—	—	—	—	28.10(30)

*dava becomes primary ligand (A) in the ternary systems; standard deviation in parenthesis.

^aRef. 4, ^bRef. 5.

The $\Delta \log K_{Cu(AH)B}$ (= log β_{CuAHB} - log β_{CuAH} - log β_{CuB}) values obtained in all the four systems do not deviate much from the statistical values⁶. This parameter obtained in the Cu^{II}-dava(A)-ahba(B) system is -3.98. This more negative value can be accounted by considering the fact that for computing this factor the log β_{CuB} value used is for the tridentate binding of ahba in its CuB binary complex, though it binds in bidentate mode in the Cu(AH)B species. Since the chelates of different sizes would bring in more ligand field in metal complexes, one can expect more positive $\Delta \log$

K_{CuAHB} values for the 5 and 6, and 5 and 7 membered rings respectively, in the Cu^{II} -dava(A)-3aba and 4aba(B) systems compared to the 5 and 5 membered rings in the Cu^{II} -dava(A)-2aba(B) system. This is actually the trend observed (Table 2). The species distribution plots obtained indicate that the formation of $\text{Cu}(\text{AH})\text{B}$ species commences at pH 4 and the maximum amount has been found to be present in the pH range 7.0–7.3, accounting 40–43% of the total metal ion in the Cu^{II} -dava(A)-2aba, 4aba and ahba(B) systems, and it is 60% in the 3aba(B) ligand system indicating that 5 and 6 membered chelates in this system are more preferred.

Table 2. Stability constants of the ternary complexes of Cu^{II} -dava(A)-2aba, 3aba, 4aba and ahba(B) systems*

Parameter	2aba	3aba	4aba	ahba
$\log \beta_{\text{CuAHB}}$	24.73(7)	24.22(5)	23.48(8)	26.71(9)
$\log \beta_{\text{CuAB}}$	15.41(4)	15.24(6)	14.34(9)	17.54(3)
$\text{p}K_{\text{CuAHB}}^{\text{H}}$	9.29	8.98	9.14	9.17
$\log K_{\text{CuAHB}}^{\text{CuA}}$	7.06	6.55	5.81	9.04
$\log K_{\text{CuAHB}}^{\text{CuB}}$	16.63	17.06	17.41	13.69
$\log P$	14.51	14.00	13.26	16.49
$\Delta \log K_{\text{CuAHB}}$	-1.04	-0.61	-0.26	-3.98
$\log K_{\text{CuAB}}^{\text{CuB}}$	7.34	8.08	8.27	4.52

*Standard deviation in parenthesis.

Stability and structure of CuAB complexes. The $\log K_{\text{CuAB}}^{\text{CuB}}$ values in the Cu^{II} -dava(A)-2aba, 3aba and 4aba(B) systems (Table 2) correspond to the glycine-like mode of binding of dava(A) in the CuAB complexes. The $\log K_{\text{CuAB}}^{\text{CuA}}$ values could not be calculated in all the four systems because $\log \beta$ value for the CuA dava species was not available. However, the comparable $\log \beta_{\text{CuAB}}$ values in the Cu^{II} -dava(A)-2aba, 3aba and 4aba(B) systems (Table 2) with those in the Cu^{II} - α -alanine(A)-2aba, 3aba and 4aba(B) systems⁵ indicate that in the CuAB complexes in Cu^{II} -dava(A)-2aba, 3aba and 4aba(B) systems, dava(A) binds like α -alanine, i.e. in a glycine-like mode, and 2aba, 3aba and 4aba are bidentate resulting in the formation of 5 and 5, 5 and 6, and 5 and 7 membered chelate rings respective-

ly in the three systems. It may be noted that $\log K_{\text{CuAB}}^{\text{CuB}}$ value obtained in ahba(B) system is ~4 log units less compared to that in the other three systems (Table 2). This indicates that ahba(B) binds in a bidentate mode in the CuAB species, though it is terdentate in the CuBahba binary species⁴. Statistical parameter, $\Delta \log K_{\text{CuAB}}$ could not be calculated in all the four systems because $\log \beta_{\text{CuA}}$ value was not available.

In all the systems, formation of CuAB species has been found to commence near pH 7.0 and there is a steady increase in its concentration with the rise in pH, accounting to 52–55% of the total metal ion, except in the 3aba(B) secondary ligand system where 70% of the total metal ion has been found to be present indicating that the formation of 5 and 6 membered chelates is more preferred.

Experimental

The stock solution of copper(II) perchlorate and other reagents were prepared as described earlier². All the ligands were Fluka Puriss quality. The pH-titrations for the mixed ligand complex systems were done with 50 cm³ solutions having low concentrations of $\text{Cu}(\text{ClO}_4)_2$: ligand A : ligand B of 1 : 1 : 1, with known volumes of standard carbonate-free NaOH. Computation was done with the aid of MINQUAD-75 computer program³ on a CYBER 180/830 A computer.

References

1. "Metal Ions in Biological Systems", ed. H. Sigel, Marcel Dekker, New York, 1971-1992, Vols. 1-28.
2. M. S. Nair, P. T. Arasu and M. A. Neelakantan, *Indian J. Chem., Sect. A*, 1997, **36**, 879; 1998, **37**, 512; *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1998, **75**, 95.
3. P. Gans, A. Vacca and A. Sabatini, *Inorg. Chim. Acta*, 1976, **18**, 237.
4. M. S. Nair and M. Santappa, *J. Chem. Soc., Dalton Trans.*, 1981, 992.
5. M. S. Nair and M. Santappa, *Indian J. Chem., Sect. A*, 1981, **20**, 990.
6. H. Sigel in "IUPAC Coordination Chemistry", ed D. Banerjee, Pergamon, Oxford, 1980.